

EXERCISES USED IN TEACHING DRAWING AND THEIR ANALYSIS

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Abstract: *There is a growing interest in the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process. Based on this, we also presented information about the exercises used in teaching drawing and their analysis.*

Key words: *drawing, education, innovation, analysis, exercise, teacher.*

The basis for improving the system of higher education in Uzbekistan are the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education” and “On the National Program for Training Personnel”. They are aimed at forming a new generation of personnel with a high general and professional culture, creative and socially active, able to act independently in social and political life, able to set and solve long-term tasks. As stated in the Concept for the Improvement of Higher Technical Education, one of the important tasks of the National Program is "reorganization of the content and structure of personnel training, taking into account the prospects for the country's socio-economic development, the needs of society, and modern achievements." in science, technology and culture.

There are many types of training courses. The most common of them are problem-solving exercises, creating problem situations in the classroom, competent, programmed (programmed) teacher training, stratification of training exercises for students, case approach, knowledge control, discussions, conversations, explanatory exercises, independent work, comparisons and comparisons, excursions, use of study guides, etc. There are several tools available to help you develop the cognitive skills listed above. Therefore, to facilitate our further analysis, we will divide the development tools used in school practice into the following three groups.

The first group includes the development of the student's personality and cognitive activity, the second group includes the mobilization of students' cognitive abilities to perform educational tasks, the third group includes the means of developing cognitive activity.

As mentioned above, the first group of developmental approaches is focused on two main goals: one is to develop cognitive activity, the other is to structure the thinking of students.

Although the development of the student's personality is carried out in the process of forming his cognitive activity, we do not believe that the above two components can be separated from each other, but, in our opinion, it is advisable to classify it when solving the problem of cognitive development.

There are two ways to develop a student's personality:

The first is to develop and improve thinking, and the second is to structure certain personality traits.

Since the activation of thinking is a key link in the development of cognitive activity, below we will dwell in more detail on the means of this group.

As for the formation of certain qualities of a student's personality, in this case the means of independence, activity, creativity, enthusiasm and other personality traits are used.

The second group of means of cognitive development is designed to mobilize the cognitive abilities of the student to solve specific actions.

Basically there are two ways to do this. Firstly, to help students complete tasks through various means, and secondly, to stimulate students' interest in reading by influencing the motivational aspects of the student's personality. These include creating the emotional state of students in the lesson, presenting educational material with tasks, demonstrating experience at the beginning of the lesson, and other means.

Learning by forcing students without any interest can suppress their inclination to learn.

The third group of tools that activate the cognitive abilities of students is to prevent the loss of time in learning in exchange for the activation of the cognitive process, allowing the mind to work with optimal tension. This group may include a variety of didactic tools (computers, drawing tools, etc.) that facilitate the work of students.

The use of ready-made handout didactic materials in teaching drawing can save a lot of time. In particular, it takes twice as long to solve a graphical problem. From this point of view, ready-made handouts used in teaching drawing can also be included in the list of activators. These tools create a wide range of opportunities and conditions for students to change their learning activities from time to time, taking into account the saved time in the classroom.

Problem-based learning occupies a special place in the organization and management of independent educational activities of students. However, in recent years, the problematic method of teaching in schools seems to be in

decline. The main reason for this is, on the one hand, the difficulty of solving the learning task step by step within the given time budget, and on the other hand, the lack of evidence-based recommendations for teachers on this teaching method.

It is well known that in order for thinking to be active, it is necessary to set a learning task for the student and ask him to find the answer. However, it should be noted that no task can ensure the active functioning of thinking. This is because the typical exercises used in training are different from the exercises that require research. Therefore, not all learning tasks are a problem.

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